

PUPILS' SELF-ESTEEM, SCHOOL ENGAGEMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR A PROGRAM DEVELOPMENT

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Pupils' Self-Esteem, School Engagement and Academic Performance: Basis for a Program Development

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Abstract

The study attempted to investigate the determinants of self-esteem, academic performance and student engagement at Doña Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School for the SY 2022-2023. The study employed descriptive research design utilizing survey questionnaires to gather data on self-esteem perceptions and involvement in activities. Academic performance data were collected through documentary analysis. The total sample size based on the computation was 233 but the actual number of respondents surveyed was 320 respondents. The perceptions of the respondents about the pupils' self-esteem when computed the average of the pupils is 4.40, while the parents' is 4.44 which are both interpreted as "Always". In addition, the extent of pupils' engagement as perceived by the parents and pupil respondents showed a remarkable alignment in their views on certain given aspects. Moreso, the level of performance of the pupil respondents during the 4th quarter showed that most of them performed well academically. Furthermore, there is enough evidence that showed a Significant Relationship between the pupils' school engagement and the academic performance. A development program entitled Program Strengthening Empowerment Leadership for Self-Acceptance (SELF) was designed based on the result of the study.

Keywords: *self-esteem, school engagement, academic performance*

Introduction

Education is universally recognized as the answer to the socioeconomic problems of the world. Nations and individuals look up to education to provide a cure for poverty, ignorance, drought, excessive rainfall, mental deficiency, joblessness, bad government, poor communication system, hunger, and inadequate shelter among other things.

It is stated in DepEd Order No. 45 s. 2009 no. 3 that the personal safety lessons shall serve as the guiding principles for the children's personal safety and protective behavior. They also enhance their social skills, self-esteem and the vital knowledge of their rights, as provided in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), codified within the context of the Filipino culture.

The enclosed guidelines are hereby issued to serve as the primary and guiding parameters in the implementation of PSL in all schools in the country. These PSL will help students uplift their Self Esteem through Personal Safety lessons.

Self-esteem is how people feel about themselves and how much they like themselves, especially socially and academically when it comes to college students. Having one's academic achievement is a major key to most college students' self-esteem. Having a high self-esteem has many positive effects and benefits, especially among college students. Students who feel positive about themselves have fewer sleepless nights, succumb less easily to pressures of conformity by peers, are less likely to use drugs and alcohol, are more persistent at difficult tasks, are happier and more sociable, and most pertinent to this study is that they tend to perform better academically.

School engagement is essential for pupils as it significantly influences their academic success and personal development. Engaged students are more likely to perform better academically, as they are actively involved in learning, motivated to achieve their goals, and committed to their education. This engagement fosters a positive attitude towards school, enhancing their desire to attend classes and participate in school activities.

The study on the determinants of self-esteem, academic performance, and student engagement at Doña Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School for the SY 2022-2023 was initiated to address critical aspects of student development and academic success. It was prompted by a recognition of the importance of educational improvement and the need to understand the factors influencing student outcomes comprehensively. By delving into the determinants of self-esteem, academic performance, and student engagement, educators and policymakers aim to craft targeted interventions and programs tailored to the specific needs of students at Doña Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School.

In addition, based on the observation of the researcher, Self-esteem is a crucial aspect of a child's emotional and psychological development. It refers to how a child views themselves, their abilities, and their worth as a person. Children with healthy self-esteem tend to have a positive outlook on life and are more resilient in the face of challenges. However, intermediate pupils (usually aged 9-12 years) may experience a variety of problems related to self-esteem. It is important for parents, teachers, and other caregivers to support intermediate pupils in developing a healthy self-esteem.

Ultimately, the study is driven by a commitment to improving educational outcomes and fostering a conducive learning environment for students. By understanding the determinants of self-esteem, academic performance, and student engagement, the research endeavors to contribute to ongoing efforts to enhance the educational experience and outcomes of students at Doña Justa Guido Memorial

Elementary School.

Research Questions

The study attempted to investigate the determinants of self-esteem, academic performance and student engagement at Doña Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School for the SY 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the parent and pupil respondents about their self-esteem in terms of:
 - 1.1. Self-Love
 - 1.2. Self-Responsibility
 - 1.3. Self-Acceptance
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the parents and the pupil respondents about their self-esteem in terms of self-love, self-responsibility and self-acceptance?
3. What are the perceptions of the parents and pupil respondents on the extent of involvement of the pupils themselves in their curricular and extracurricular activities?
4. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the abovementioned respondents on the extent of involvement of the pupils themselves in their curricular and extracurricular activities?
5. What is the level of academic performance of the pupil respondents during the 4th quarter?
6. Is there a significant relationship between self-esteem of the pupils and their academic performance?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' school engagement and their level of academic performance?
8. What development program may be crafted based on the results of the study?

Literature Review

Self-esteem, being one of the influential factors which affect the students' academic achievement received increasing attention in education research in present days. It is one's own judgment of self-worth. It is a set of attitudes and beliefs through which people positively or negatively evaluate themselves which may likewise influence their development of cognitive and affective traits in the long term. (Aryana, 2018).

In addition, self-esteem is an internal belief possessed by each person which help them to face, understand, and solve life's challenges in order to achieve good self-concept, self-confidence and happiness. In academic level, self-esteem can be defined as the evaluative appraisal of experience of being capable to meet the academic challenges (Ayodele, 2018).

In general, high self-esteem help individuals to view themselves as active and capable persons to promote changes through effort and set higher goals which cause learning new things. Interestingly, numerous researchers have demonstrated that the best way to improve student achievement is to increase their self-esteem (Amrai et al., 2018).

Self-esteem begins to be formed when we are babies. If someone feeds us and cuddles us when we cry, we feel that we are loved and valued. We begin to trust our parents or guardians, knowing that they keep us safe and well. As we get older, we look to the people around us for approval as well. The feeling that we are valued by them is the basis of our self-esteem. Furthermore, the development of self-esteem is somewhat exceptional; if good things happen, self-esteem is high while if it is the other way around, self-esteem is low (Baumeister et. al. 2019).

The relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement is one that is regarded by many educators as a well-established fact. This belief has been often invoked in order to argue against the provision of ability grouping for gifted students. Refuting that commonly held belief, this research examined the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in 65 high-ability secondary students, a sample drawn from a longitudinal study of over 900 students (Soliman et al., 2021).

Relatively, it was found that the factors like parent's education, parental occupation, type of family, family size, ordinal position and even gender and age of the child were found to have their impact on the academic performance of every pupil. Studies dealing with the effect of family environment on student's achievement suggested that several characteristics of family life are relevant. Academic performance has become an index of child's future in this highly competitive world. Academic performance has been one of the most important goals of the educational process. It was also a major goal, which every individual is expected to perform in all cultures. Academic performance is a key mechanism through which adolescents learn about their talents, abilities and competencies which are an important part of developing career aspirations (Cabot., 2016) academic achievement and career aspirations in adolescence are often correlated (Brophy, 2018).

Additionally, school climate plays a crucial role in student engagement. Positive interactions with teachers and peers, as well as a supportive school environment, contribute to higher levels of engagement. Conversely, a negative school climate can lead to disengagement and burnout, which negatively impact students' mental health and academic outcomes (BMC Psychology, 2021).

Furthermore, the importance of tailored teaching strategies was also emphasized in the literature. Teachers who adapt their instructional methods to meet the diverse needs of students can better engage them. Active learning, collaborative activities, and providing choices in learning tasks were shown to be effective in maintaining high levels of student engagement (Han, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive survey was used in this study in order to ascertain the Determinants of Self-Esteem and Academic Performance of Intermediate Pupils at Dona Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School. According to Babie (2019), descriptive survey study is concerned with the prevailing or existing status of an event or problem. In this method, the researcher aimed to describe the existing phenomenon with the purpose of exploring the causes of a particular problem. It was used to realize the Pupils' Self-Esteem, School Engagement and Academic Performance at Dona Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School

Furthermore, according to Creswell (2019), correlation is concerned in determining the relationship that exists between two variables. This method helped the researcher to quantify the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the intermediate pupils and parents at Dona Justa Guido Memorial Elementary School. There were 320 actual surveyed pupil respondents out of 558 target respondents. This is more than the minimum sample size (n) based on the 5% margin of error.

Instrument

The instrument that was used in the study was the researcher-made questionnaire-checklist. Part I of the questionnaire included the parents' and student-respondent perceptions about the self-esteem of the students in terms of self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance. While Part II included items to determine the perceptions of the parents and pupils on the extent of the pupils' involvement in curricular and extracurricular activities.

Procedure

The researcher requested approval to conduct a study from the School's Division Superintendent. Upon approval, the letter was forwarded to the school principal. Moreover, parent consent was given to the parents of the pupils of the intermediate levels, namely grade 4, 5, and 6. After the parent consent was signed, distribution of survey questionnaire was done. This was personally done by the researcher with the assistance from the class advisers of the pupils. The instruments were collected and tallied for data analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed the necessary ethics in his conduct of study. He informed the respondents regarding their involvement in the study and sought their consent and ensured them that the data collected are for the use of the study only and the data privacy law will be observed.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Perception of the parent and pupil respondents about their self-esteem in terms of Self-Love, Self-Responsibility and Self-Acceptance

Table 1. *Perception of the Pupils and Parents respondent about their self-esteem in terms of Self-Love*

	Self-Love	Pupils		Parents	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	I have a positive attitude towards myself and my abilities.	4.18	Frequent	4.13	Frequent
2.	I treat myself with kindness and respect.	4.65	Always	4.67	Always
3.	I am proud of who I am and what I can accomplish.	4.77	Always	4.75	Always
4.	I embrace my uniqueness and celebrate my individuality.	3.97	Frequent	3.95	Frequent
5.	I prioritize self-care and prioritize my well-being	4.55	Always	4.53	Always
Average mean		4.43	Always	4.41	Always
Standard Deviation		0.46		0.45	

Despite these variations, both groups demonstrated an overall high level of agreement with statements concerning self-love, as evidenced by their respective overall mean scores of 4.43 for pupils and 4.41 for parents. Results imply that Table 3 underscored the importance of reinforcing positive attitudes and celebrating achievements to foster and maintain high levels of self-esteem among pupils. While there exists a strong consensus between pupils and parents regarding pride in identity and accomplishments, the slightly lower scores associated with embracing individuality suggest an area for improvement.

This conforms the study of Aryana (2018) which claimed that by creating a supportive environment that values and celebrates individual differences, educators and parents can play a pivotal role in nurturing pupils' confidence and resilience.

Table 2. *Computed Mean of the Perception of the Pupils and Parents Respondents about their self-esteem in terms of Self-Responsibility*

	Self-Responsibility	Pupils		Parents	
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1.	I take responsibility for my actions and their outcomes.	4.53	Always	4.58	Always
2.	I complete my tasks and assignments on time	4.64	Always	4.63	Always
3.	I am proactive in identifying and addressing my own needs.	4.23	Always	4.28	Always
4.	I am accountable for my learning and personal growth.	4.40	Always	4.40	Always
5.	I show initiative and take the lead in my responsibilities	4.04	Frequent	4.10	Frequent
Average mean		4.37	Always	4.40	Always
Standard Deviation		0.57		0.54	

The data imply a strong consensus between pupils and parents regarding the pupils' self-esteem in terms of self-responsibility. The implications include recognizing and reinforcing the already-established sense of responsibility for actions and tasks while exploring strategies to further promote accountability for learning, personal growth, and taking initiative in responsibilities. Continued support for the proactive identification and addressing of personal needs is also essential to maintain and enhance the positive self-esteem identified in this assessment. Results support Finn and Zimmerman (2019). Their research focuses on self-regulated learning, a concept closely related to self-responsibility, and explores how metacognitive awareness and goal setting influence academic performance and personal responsibility.

Table 3. *Computed Mean of the Perception of the Pupils and Parents-Respondents about their self-esteem in terms of Self-Acceptance*

	Self-Acceptance	Pupils		Parents	
		Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1.	I accept myself for who I am, without trying to be someone else.	4.70	Always	4.71	Always
2.	I embrace my strengths and weaknesses without judgment.	4.39	Always	4.46	Always
3.	I am confident in my abilities and value my own worth.	4.67	Always	4.66	Always
4.	I celebrate my achievements and learn from my mistakes.	4.36	Always	4.37	Always
5.	I resist the pressure to conform and stay true to my authentic self.	4.33	Always	4.36	Always
Average Mean		4.49	Always	4.51	Always
Standard Deviation		0.65		0.62	

The implications include reinforcing and celebrating the pupils' ability to accept themselves authentically, embracing strengths and weaknesses, and resisting societal pressures. Additionally, efforts can be directed towards boosting confidence in abilities and reinforcing the value of one's worth. Overall, maintaining and enhancing this positive self-perception can contribute to a strong foundation of self-acceptance among pupils. Results support the study of Neff's (2019) research on self-compassion. Neff's study examined the construct of self-compassion, defined as the ability to treat oneself with kindness, recognize one's shared humanity, and be mindful of one's experiences without judgment.

Significant Difference between the parent and pupil respondents about their self-esteem in terms of Self-Love, Self-Responsibility and Self-Acceptance

Table 4. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Parents and the Pupil-Respondents About Their Self-Esteem in Terms of Self-Love, Self-Responsibility and Self-Acceptance*

Aspects	Respondents	WM	Sd	Comp z	Crit.z Value	Decision	VI
Self- Love	Pupils	4.43	0.46	0.52	1.96	Fail to Reject H ₀	NS
	Parents	4.41	0.45				
Self-Responsibility	Pupils	4.37	0.57	0.56	1.96	Fail to Reject H ₀	NS
	Parents	4.40	0.54				
Self-Acceptance	Pupils	4.49	0.65	0.46	1.96	Fail to Reject H ₀	NS
	Parents	4.51	0.62				

Results imply that both parents and pupils have similar views on these aspects of self-esteem. One implication of this finding is that interventions aimed at enhancing self-esteem in young individuals could potentially benefit from involving parents in the process. By recognizing and aligning parental and pupil perspectives, interventions can be more holistic and effective in promoting healthy self-esteem development. Results supported study by Stork et al. (2018) which explored the role of parental involvement in adolescents' self-esteem development. The study found that parental support and encouragement significantly contributed to higher levels of self-esteem in adolescents.

Perception of the parent and pupil respondents on the extent of involvement of pupils in the curricular and extra-curricular activities

The data imply a shared understanding between pupils and parents regarding academic responsibilities, while also signaling potential

opportunities for further encouragement and support in expanding extracurricular pursuits. The detailed comparison provides valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of pupils' engagement as perceived by both primary stakeholders.

Table 5. *Extent of Pupils' Engagement as Perceived by Pupils and Parents Respondents*

<i>Extent of Pupils' Engagement</i>		<i>Pupils</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I actively participate in class discussions and contribute my ideas and opinions.	4.11	Frequent	4.10	Frequent
2.	I complete my assignments and homework promptly, taking my academic responsibilities seriously.	4.79	Always	4.73	Always
3.	I actively seek out and participate in extracurricular activities that align with my interests and hobbies.	3.94	Frequent	3.99	Frequent
4.	I enjoy learning and take the initiative to explore additional resources and topics beyond what is taught in class.	4.73	Always	4.70	Always
5.	I strive to maintain a healthy balance between my academic workload and my involvement in extracurricular activities	4.60	Always	4.60	Always
6.	I feel that my teachers provide opportunities for active involvement in class activities and projects.	4.62	Always	4.58	Always
7.	I receive feedback and recognition for my participation and contributions in curricular activities.	4.11	Frequent	4.10	Frequent
8.	I feel supported by my school in pursuing and participating in extracurricular activities that interest me.	3.89	Frequent	3.97	Frequent
9.	I believe that my school values the importance of a balanced education that includes both curricular and extracurricular activities.	4.58	Always	4.57	Always
10.	I feel that my school maintains open communication with students regarding curricular and extracurricular activities.	4.54	Always	4.55	Always
Average Mean		4.39	Always	4.39	Always
Standard Deviation		0.42		0.45	

The data imply a shared understanding between pupils and parents regarding academic responsibilities, while also signaling potential opportunities for further encouragement and support in expanding extracurricular pursuits. The detailed comparison provides valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of pupils' engagement as perceived by both primary stakeholders.

Results supported the study of Fredricks et al. (2020). Their research focuses on the multidimensional nature of student engagement and its impact on academic outcomes. Through a comprehensive analysis, Fredricks et al. identified three dimensions of student engagement: behavioral engagement, emotional engagement, and cognitive engagement.

Significant Difference between the perception of the parents and pupils on the extent of involvement of the pupils in the curricular and extracurricular activities

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perception of the Parents and Pupils on the Extent of Involvement of the Pupils in the Curricular and Extracurricular Activities*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Computed Z Value</i>	<i>Critical z-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pupils	4.39	0.42	0.00	1.96	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
Parents	4.39	0.45				

Since the computed z value of 0.00 was less than the critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the perception of the parents and pupils on the extent of involvement of the pupils in the curricular and extracurricular activities. The data imply that both the pupils and parents have the same point-of-view on the possible effect of pupil's involvement in the curricular and extracurricular activities.

Results supported the study of Hoover-Dempsey et al (2019). Their research investigates the role of parental involvement in students' academic experiences and achievement outcomes.

Level of Academic Performance of the Pupils during the 4th Quarter

Table 7. *Frequency and Percentage of Level of Academic Performance of the Pupils' Respondents during the 4th Quarter*

<i>Verbal Descriptors</i>	<i>Grade Scale</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Outstanding	90 – 100	6	2%
Very Satisfactory	85 – 89	132	41%
Satisfactory	80 – 84	136	43%
Fairly Satisfactory	75 – 79	46	14%
Did Not Meet the Expectations	Below 75	0	0%
N		320	100%

The data from the table indicated that during the 4th quarter, most pupils performed quite well academically. The data imply that the majority of pupils demonstrated good academic performance, with a significant proportion achieving above-average grades. This suggests that the educational efforts during the 4th quarter were effective in supporting students' learning and development.

Results supported the study of Hattie, J. (2019), titled "Visible Learning: A Synthesis of Over 800 Meta-Analyses Relating to Achievement." Hattie's research provides comprehensive insights into the factors influencing student achievement across various educational contexts.

Significant Relationship between the Self-Esteem of the Pupils and the Academic Performance during the 4th Quarter

Table 8. Test of Significant Relationship between the Self-esteem of the Pupils and Academic Performance

Self-Esteem	Pearson's <i>r</i>	VI	Critical z-value	<i>p</i> Value	Decision	VI
Self-Love (Pagmamahal sa Sarili)	0.08	Negligible	1.96	0.17	Fail to reject H_0	Not Significant
Self-Responsibility (Pagiging Responsable sa Sarili)	0.03	Negligible		0.56	Fail to reject H_0	Not Significant
Self-Acceptance (Pangtanggap sa Sarili)	0.03	Negligible		0.61	Fail to reject H_0	Not Significant

The critical z-value of 1.96 in the table indicated the threshold for determining statistical significance at the 0.05 level. Since none of the observed z-values for the relationships between self-esteem components and academic performance reach or exceed this critical value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected, indicating no significant relationships were found. These data revealed that students' self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance have no connections in their academic performance.

A related study that could provide further insights into the relationship between self-esteem and academic performance was conducted by Baumeister et al. (2019) which critically examined the often-assumed positive effects of high self-esteem across various domains, including academic performance.

Significant relationship between the pupil's school engagement and the level of their Academic Performance

Table 9. Test of Significant Relationship between the Pupils' School Engagement and Academic Performance

Aspects	Pearson's <i>r</i>	VI	<i>p</i> Value	Decision	VI
Pupils' School Engagement Academic Performance	0.64	Strong	0.00	Reject H_0	Significant

Since the computed *p* value of 0.00 was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there was enough evidence that this relationship is significant. The implication of this result is that efforts to enhance student engagement in various aspects of school life, such as classroom participation, extracurricular involvement, and overall enthusiasm for learning, may lead to improved academic performance.

Results supported the study of Fredricks et al (2020). Their research highlights the significance of students' active participation, enthusiasm, and meaningful connections to learning in predicting academic success.

Proposed Development Program

Program SELF: Strengthening Empowerment Leadership For Self-acceptance

Rationale:

Based on the results of assessments and feedback, it has been identified that the lowest means lie within the domains of self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance among participants. These areas are critical components of overall well-being and personal development. Addressing these areas is essential for fostering a positive self-perception, encouraging proactive behavior, and promoting authenticity.

Self-Love:

Participants have reported lower scores in affirming positive attitudes towards themselves and their abilities. Developing self-love is fundamental for building self-esteem and resilience. Without a strong foundation of self-love, individuals may struggle to overcome challenges and setbacks effectively.

Self-Responsibility:

The data indicate that participants exhibit less initiative and leadership in their responsibilities. Cultivating self-responsibility is crucial for personal growth and success. Taking ownership of one's actions and responsibilities is essential for achieving goals and fulfilling potential.

Self-Acceptance:

Participants have expressed difficulties in resisting external pressures to conform and staying true to their authentic selves. Embracing self-acceptance is vital for fostering authenticity and living a fulfilling life. Without self-acceptance, individuals may experience inner conflict and dissatisfaction, hindering their overall well-being.

Addressing these areas through targeted interventions and support mechanisms will empower participants to develop a stronger sense of self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance. By addressing the root causes of these challenges, participants can enhance their overall well-being, personal growth, and resilience.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

There was a consensus between parents and pupils that cultivating self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance was crucial for enhancing self-esteem.

Both the pupils and their parents had similar views about self-esteem in terms of self-love, self-responsibility, and self-acceptance.

Self-esteem showed no significant correlation with academic success, indicating that factors beyond self-esteem played a more pivotal role in determining students' achievements.

Engagement in school activities, including extracurricular participation, influenced academic performance, suggesting a mutual influence between involvement and achievement.

The higher the level of engagement, the higher was the possibility of achieving higher academic performance.

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